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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
EC	European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PO	Project Officer

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is the deliverable D9.7, entitled CitySCAPE Communication Tools, which is prepared within the WP9 framework of the CitySCAPE project.

CitySCAPE communication tools will form a coherent visual and brand identity for the project and maximize penetration and comprehension of the project key messages to appropriate audiences. To address the first point, a coherent visual identity has been created for the project that will be applied in all relevant tools. For the second point, various tools will be realized to use different channels and enable a multi-level communication strategy.

The CitySCAPE Communication Tools will include both paper and electronic means. Therefore, they will cover all kinds of communication activities and contain all possible information that the project would like to publish for communication purposes. The communication tools will be updated alongside the communication strategy, not only in terms of content but also in design, when needed. Emphasis will be given on the use of communication tools on activities and channels that will maximize the project results impact while still providing the general CitySCAPE vision.

CitySCAPE Communication Tools will be available to the entire consortium for use and they will be used in both consortium and partner-specific events.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Introduction

The traditional security controls and security assurance arguments are becoming increasingly inefficient in supporting the emerging needs and applications of the interconnecting transport systems, allowing threats and security incidents to disturb all transportation dimensions.

CitySCAPE is a project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, which consists of 15 partners from 6 European countries, united in their vision to cover the cybersecurity needs of multimodal transportation.

More specifically, the CitySCAPE software toolkit will:

- ✓ Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats
- ✓ Evaluate an attack's impact in both technical and financial terms
- ✓ Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero-day attacks
- ✓ Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT/CSIRT authorities and support their interplay

The project duration extends from September 2020 to August 2023.

1.2 Deliverable Purpose

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide insight and detailed information for the CitySCAPE Communication Tools. The project communication tools are based on the same visual identity patterns and will be used for intra- and extra-project purposes. Thus, communication tools include, amongst other, standard project templates, posters and brochures, press releases and videos, e-newsletters, social media presence and the project website.

Communication tools are and will be designed to be easily accessed and used by all project partners. All partners need to be aware of the available tools and use them at any given chance to produce a coherent brand identity for the project. All partners' contribution in creating the content of the project communication tools is also essential to reflect both project and partners' work under the CitySCAPE framework.

1.3 Intended Readership

This deliverable is disseminated internally within the project consortium and externally to interested parties outside the project. The intended readership primarily comprises the members of the CitySCAPE consortium, the European Commission (EC) and the CitySCAPE Project Officer (PO).

The specific document could be used as a reference point by the consortium partners to use the same and appropriate communication tools for CitySCAPE.

2 VISUAL IDENTITY

The CitySCAPE project has been trying to build a strong visual identity through effective branding and delivering clear messages to a variety of target audiences, since the launch of the project. To this end, a project's logo, project's templates as well as a dedicated brand book and a colour palette were created to build a consistent appearance that will be used throughout the whole project in all applicable communication and dissemination channels (website, leaflets, poster, templates, and presentations). This is the most effective way to ensure that a consistent identity of CitySCAPE is widely communicated. The project's logo, brand book, colour palette and templates are described in detail in chapter 3 of the deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan that was submitted in M6.

2.1 EU Acknowledgement

The EU Acknowledgement and the EU flag should be included in all dissemination and communication activities and material so that it is always clearly stated that the project is funded by the EU. The use of the EU Acknowledgement is described in detail in chapter 6.4 of the deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan that was submitted in M6.

3 COMMUNICATION KIT

A Communication Kit that includes suitable and important dissemination and communication material has been created since the beginning of the project and it will be enhanced with more material the next months.

3.1 Brochure, Poster and Roll –up Banner

The first version of the promotional brochure of the CitySCAPE project has been completed by month 3 of the project's lifetime. The brochure, poster and roll up banner are described in detail in chapter 4.2.1 of the deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan that was submitted in M6. A second version will be available in the third phase of the project.

3.2 Pilot Factsheets

CitySCAPE will create pilot factsheets for each of the CitySCAPE pilot use cases. More details can be found in chapter 4.2.2 of the deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan that was submitted in M6.

3.3 Video

The CitySCAPE video for which you can find details in chapter 4.2.3 of the deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan that was submitted in M6, will be created in the third phase of the project.

3.4 E-newsletters

Five e-newsletters will be issued around major project milestones. The first issue was published in M12 and was sent to multiple contacts registered via the website, was circulated on the project's social media and has been available on the official [website](#) in downloadable format.

CitySCAPE is a 36-month project that introduces innovative risk analysis techniques and orchestrates a number of software solutions to realize an interoperable toolkit that seamlessly integrates to any multimodal transport system and will provide a scheme for cyber security labelling for City-level multimodal transport.

[Read More](#)

CitySCAPE Project Meetings

[Kick off Meeting](#)

Figure 1: CitySCAPE 1st newsletter

3.5 General Presentation

A CitySCAPE general presentation had been created since the beginning of the project. The presentation includes general information about the project such as the consortium partners, the duration, the website and social media, the aim and objectives of the project and information about the pilot demonstrations.

The general presentation can be used with no prior approval from the consortium to conferences and events.

Project at a Glance

CitySCAPE

- Call identifier: H2020-SU-DS-2019
- Topic: SU-DS05-2018-2019 - Digital security, privacy, data protection and accountability in critical sectors
- EC Funding: 6 293 011,25 €
- Duration: 36 months
- Consortium: 15 partners
- Coordinator: Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICSS), Greece – Dr. Angelos Arditis (a.arditis@iccs.gr)
- Learn more: www.cityscape-project.eu
- Join us: [@EUCityscape](https://twitter.com/EUCityscape) [CitySCAPE Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/cityscape-project/)

14/12/2022

Footer

Slide 2 of 10 English (United States)

Figure 2: CitySCAPE general presentation

4 ELECTRONIC MEDIA

4.1 Website

The project's website, www.cityscape-project.eu, is one of the most important communication channels of the CitySCAPE project. It will serve as a vital element of engagement with the identified key audiences. It will provide information about the project, such as a general description of the project, the project objectives and impact, its consortium, project events, significant events of the Cybersecurity and Transport sector and project news. Project presentations from events, scientific publications, the public deliverables and the executive summaries of all the confidential deliverables will be available on the website, providing the necessary information regarding the project's progress and outcomes. In general, the website will present and explain in simple terms what the project is about and why the key audiences and the public should be interested in it.

The website's design and layout align with the CitySCAPE brand identity and are visually attractive, informative and easy to navigate. The website is dynamic and flexible in terms of structure and functionality to develop and expand to meet the project's changing requirements over time. Moreover, it is created with responsive web design techniques that make it applicable and fitting to all devices.

4.1.1 Hosting and running

The server is hosted in the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) premises in Athens, Greece. The website has been developed in a mobile-friendly mode using WordPress Content Management System and is compatible with all available web browsers (Internet Explorer, Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, etc.). The Content Management System and the design are developed and customized by ICCS for the purposes of CitySCAPE.

4.1.2 Structure and Content

The homepage is the entry point for site visitors by presenting essential project information while using a simple layout to focus on the branding and facilitate navigation. The header area contains the project logo and the main upper navigation menu. Just below that, information about the CitySCAPE project, the objectives, the expected impact, the use cases and the consortium provide visitors with direct access to main project information without further search on the website. Moreover, there is a section dedicated to upcoming events in the Cybersecurity and Transport sector. The visitors can also register for the project's newsletter and follow its social media in the same section. Finally, the footnote of the homepage includes the EU flag and the respective acknowledgment text, an imprint section, which includes a disclaimer notice and website information, links to the CitySCAPE social media channels, and the Project Coordinator's contact

details. This footnote appears not only on the homepage but also on all website pages, ensuring EU funding visibility.

The layout of the CitySCAPE website homepage is shown in [Annex 1](#).

The horizontal drop-down navigation menu comprises the following pages and sub pages:

- **About:** presents the project's concept, objectives and impact.
- **News**
 - **Project News:** this page contains news related to the CitySCAPE project, such as participation in events, publications, newsletters etc
 - **Events:** This page includes the most important events of the Cybersecurity and Transport sector as well as project's events (plenary meetings, review meetings)
 - **Blog:** this page includes articles written by the consortium's partners regarding their work within the project or regarding cybersecurity and multimodal transportation, in general.
- **Consortium:** this page contains the CitySCAPE consortium along with each partner's official website.
- **Material Hub**
 - **Dissemination Material:** this page contains the project's promotional material, all available for download
 - **Deliverables:** this page contains a list of the project's deliverables and will include links to download the public deliverables and an executive summary of the confidential ones.
 - **Media Centre:** this page includes all the press releases and press activities regarding the project.
 - **Newsletters:** this page will include the five CitySCAPE e-newsletters, all available for download
 - **Audio-Visual Material:** this page will include photos and videos from communication events and project meetings.
 - **Publications/Presentations:** this page contains information about project-related publications to scientific journals and conference proceedings as well as project presentations
- **H2020 Synergies:** this section presents H2020 funded projects with which CitySCAPE has already collaborated or will collaborate in the future.

4.1.3 Updating

ICCS, being the WP9 leader is responsible for updating the website regularly. The project website facilitates a broad range of communication activities. Project news and events will be posted systematically. Information on the project's deliverables and press activities will be uploaded and updated frequently.

4.1.4 Monitoring

The website visiting tracker software Google Analytics has been added to the website and will provide at regular reporting times detailed insights into

the CitySCAPE website traffic. Google Analytics tools are useful as they allow for measuring website traffic patterns; the number and duration of visits, the number of page views, the visitors' geographical location, correlation with the timing of the project events, etc. This information can be used to optimize the structure, the content and the design of the website to match its visitors' preferences. To ensure GDPR compliance we have created a cookie consent banner created by the consent management platform [Cookiebot](#).

Here are the options in the compliant cookie consent banner from which the visitor can choose from:

- ✓ A button to accept cookies: An opt-in approach is the safest way to stay compliant with the GDPR. Additionally, the cookie banner text explicitly makes clear that clicking the button means the user agrees to the use of all cookies.
- ✓ A button to deny the use of all cookies, except for those that allow the website to function on the user's browser, and
- ✓ A button that leads to detailed information about how we use cookies: We are explicit about the reasons you use cookies, stating whether cookies are used for social media, analytics advertising, or for sharing data with third parties, etc
- ✓ A link to the whole Cookie Policy: This policy lists the cookies we use and the purpose of each.

A link to your cookie settings so that users have the option to manage which cookies they will or will not accept. This is not actually a requirement of the GDPR, but it is a best practice.

4.2 Social Media

Social media¹ allow us to reach an extremely wide — but also targeted — audience, maximising the impact and successful exploitation of our research results. Therefore, the project will make extended use of social media platforms, namely Twitter and LinkedIn, in order to raise awareness and communicate the project's progress and results, as well as to diffuse the project's news and activities. ICCS is managing the accounts daily and is updating their content.

4.2.1 Twitter

The CitySCAPE Twitter account is used to raise awareness of the project, especially for the wider cyber security and transport community and has been created at an early stage of the project, prior to its kick-off. Twitter is a social networking platform that is ideal for spreading news and engaging with users in real-time. [@EUCityscape](#) is interacting with relevant accounts, communicating the project's vision and progress. Currently, the CitySCAPE twitter account has 614 followers while following 596 twitter accounts.

¹ [H2020 Programme_Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects](#)

Figure 3: CitySCAPE Twitter account

4.2.2 LinkedIn

The CitySCAPE LinkedIn account has been also set up well in advance to attract interested stakeholders. LinkedIn is the most popular professional network on the internet. Registered members are able to establish connections with professionals who are in their interest and interact in group discussions. [CitySCAPE LinkedIn](#) account will enable to build a strong network with some of the project's key audiences, such as research institutes, industry, policymakers and individuals involved in the cybersecurity and transport sector. So far, the project account has 194 followers.

Figure 4: CitySCAPE LinkedIn account

4.3 Online Platforms

4.3.1 CitySCAPE Zenodo Community

This [Community](#) will include all the public information regarding the project. By now, the dissemination material (brochure, poster, banner, newsletter, brand book, colour palette, logo) has been uploaded, and it is available publicly. Moreover, all the public deliverables, once the EC approves them, will be uploaded along with all the scientific papers that will be submitted by the consortium partners. Therefore, everyone interested in the project or similar projects and research can access and download this material.

Figure 5: CitySCAPE Zenodo Community

4.3.2 Cyberwatching.eu

The [Cyberwatching.eu](https://www.cyberwatching.eu) project hub is a complete and unabridged compilation of EU-funded research projects on cybersecurity topics. It was created specifically to facilitate information transfer, communication and cross-pollination. CitySCAPE's profile is available [here](#).

Figure 6: CitySCAPE's profile in Cyberwatching.eu

5 PRESS ACTIVITIES

The project's press releases will be developed by ICCS upon specific project's achievements and distributed to several media communication channels such as local or national radio, television and online press. The CitySCAPE partners will use their press contacts to communicate the developments of the project and will be responsible for translations and regional adaptations. Partners efforts will also focus on publishing major CitySCAPE achievements through channels and means offered by the European Commission (i.e., the Horizon Magazine, research EU results magazine, Futuris Magazine etc.)

5.1 Press Releases

A kick-off press release had been created and is available on the CitySCAPE [website](#). Moreover, the press release was published in Greek by ICCS and in Italian by KSP. The press releases resulted in twenty two press clippings in popular Italian and Greek online media. Both the press releases and their press clippings are available in the [Media Center](#) section of the CitySCAPE website.

5.2 Press Activities

Besides the press releases, there has been made a special effort to communicate the project through other press media. By now, two interviews and two articles have been published in popular web media. Both the interviews and articles are available on the [Media Center](#) of the CitySCAPE website.

Figure 7: Interview about CitySCAPE

Figure 8: article about CitySCAPE (Logistics & Management GR)

Kaspersky supporta Horizon 2020 il programma promosso dalla Commissione Europea per il finanziamento di progetti di Ricerca e Innovazione

Nell'ambito di **HORIZON 2020**, il programma promosso dalla Commissione Europea per il finanziamento di progetti di Ricerca e Innovazione nascono tre progetti di innovazione nei quali Kaspersky è stato coinvolto grazie alla sua expertise nel campo della cybersecurity.

A giugno è stato lanciato **GEIGER** un progetto di innovazione ideato da un consorzio di 18 organizzazioni che ha l'obiettivo di sviluppare una soluzione che sia in grado non solo di dimostrare alle piccole imprese e agli imprenditori quali sono i rischi di sicurezza informatica per la loro azienda legati alla protezione dei dati e alla privacy ma anche di offrire assistenza per ridurre questi rischi al minimo.

Al progetto collaboreranno specialisti ed esperti di cybersecurity e centri nazionali di sicurezza informatica per sviluppare Cyber-GEIGER, un "visitatore Geiger" per la sicurezza informatica, che aiuterà le piccole imprese a prendere coscienza dei rischi ai quali sono esposte. Le piccole imprese potranno utilizzare Cyber-GEIGER dal web o dallo smartphone e ottenere tutte le informazioni sul livello di rischio attuale della propria azienda. Prendere coscienza dei rischi permette di poter rispondere in maniera efficace attraverso l'adozione di semplici misure o la richiesta di assistenza per ridurre significativamente l'esposizione al rischio.

A settembre, Kaspersky ha presentato il secondo progetto previsto dalla Commissione europea in tema di innovazione. Si tratta di **CitySCAPE** che ha lo scopo di proteggere l'ecosistema dei trasporti multimodali. Il progetto coinvolge **19 partner da 8 diversi Paesi europei**, uniti dall'obiettivo comune di soddisfare le esigenze di sicurezza informatica del trasporto multimodale. CitySCAPE introduce tecniche innovative di analisi dei rischi e gestisce una serie di soluzioni software per realizzare un toolkit interoperabile che si integri perfettamente in qualsiasi sistema di trasporto multimodale. La soluzione CitySCAPE sarà testata in due casi d'uso e nei test saranno coinvolte applicazioni di ticketing, sistemi automatici di controllo e moduli di gestione di veicoli connessi e a guida autonoma. Al fine di dimostrare l'efficacia, i due progetti pilota in CitySCAPE verranno realizzati: nel sistema di trasporto locale di Genova, in Italia e di Tallin, in Estonia.

A novembre è stato lanciato anche il terzo progetto Horizon 2020, **TRAPEZE** che si pone l'ambizioso obiettivo di guidare il cambiamento culturale nella protezione dell'economia europea dei dati ed è finalizzato allo sviluppo di una soluzione che consenta di mettere nelle mani dei cittadini UE la sicurezza e la privacy dei propri dati. Il progetto aprirà la strada all'utilizzo pratico delle tecnologie d'avanguardia a favore dei cittadini.

Grazie alla sua expertise nel campo della cybersecurity, Kaspersky è stata coinvolta nello sviluppo dei tre progetti ed è parte dei tre consorzi. L'azienda metterà a disposizione le proprie soluzioni e i servizi di sicurezza innovativi. In particolare, Kaspersky è responsabile della protezione delle applicazioni mobile attraverso l'integrazione con il Kaspersky Mobile Security Software Development Kit (KMS SDK), una soluzione che offre protezione per dispositivi mobili contro minacce note ed emergenti. Si tratta di un framework multilivello che offre una protezione online integrata direttamente nelle applicazioni mobili, proteggendo in tempo reale le informazioni inserite dagli utenti e le transazioni su dispositivi mobile con sistemi operativi Android, iOS e Windows Phone. Inoltre, Kaspersky si occuperà della formazione degli utenti attraverso la soluzione di gamification "Cyber Safety Management Games (CSMG)" o "Kaspersky Interactive Protection Simulation (KIPS)" e attraverso la soluzione di training online "Kaspersky Automated Security Awareness Platform (KASAP)". Si tratta di un programma di formazione che, attraverso il micro-apprendimento e la competizione favorisce l'impegno delle imprese e degli utenti finali verso la cybersecurity. La formazione offerta da Kaspersky fornisce competenze, conoscenze e comportamenti essenziali per mantenere un ambiente di lavoro sicuro e proteggere la propria privacy. Copre tutti i principali ambiti di sicurezza e le situazioni tipiche, inoltre, dove previsto, Kaspersky alimenterà le piattaforme di Threat Intelligence con i suoi Threat Data Feeds al fine di contribuire ad anticipare gli incidenti causati da minacce APT (Advanced Persistent Threats).

«Siamo davvero molto orgogliosi di partecipare a questi tre progetti e di poter contribuire alle soluzioni per cittadini, piccole imprese e utenti dei sistemi di trasporto multimodali con i nostri prodotti e servizi professionali nel campo della cyber security», ha dichiarato **Amedeo D'Arangelo, Enterprise Project Technical Coordinator** di Kaspersky. «Nei consorzi di cui facciamo parte siamo considerati un partner affidabile sia per merito della nostra competenza tecnica, che ci consentono di proteggere e formare aziende e utenti in ogni settore, che per la nostra cultura dell'innovazione, che ci permette di adattare prodotti e servizi e di creare di nuovi in un contesto in continua evoluzione quale quello delle minacce alla sicurezza informatica».

Figure 9: Article about CitySCAPE (Kaspersky newsletter IT)

5.3 H2020 media announcements

CitySCAPE partners make special effort in publishing CitySCAPE achievements and updates through online channels and means offered by the European Commission. CitySCAPE has made three announcements in H2020 online media by now and intends in making at least another three.

CitySCAPE: City-level Cyber-Secure Multimodal Transport Ecosystem. A new era in safety of the multimodal transport begins!

CitySCAPE is a project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, which consists of 15 partners from 6 European countries, united in their vision to cover the cybersecurity needs of the multimodal transportation. The project duration extends from September 2020 to August 2023.

Contributed by: ICDS, Genova

Related projects

HORIZON 2020

PROJECT

CitySCAPE
CitySCAPE: City-level Cyber-Secure Multimodal Transport Ecosystem

17 September 2021

© CitySCAPE

Figure 10: CitySCAPE article on CORDIS

CitySCAPE Italian Web Conference 2021

15 December 2021

Online only

This event has ended.

The webinar will focus on the Italian pilot of the CitySCAPE (2) project that will be performed in Genova and the research achievements of the Italian partners namely SIGLA, KSP, STAM, AMT, ENG of the project.

- The agenda and registration is
- The event will be held in Italian

Topic: Research and innovation

Practical information

When: 15 December 2021, 9:50 (CET)

Languages: Italian

Share this page

Figure 11: CitySCAPE announcement on Europa.eu

Figure 12: Screenshot of EU Research Result tweet

6 CONCLUSION

The project concept, goals, and expected impact will be communicated through various channels using diverse communication tools, which are being deployed selectively to ensure maximum impact.

The present deliverable presents in detail the project's available communication tools. All the tools are based on following a coherent visual scheme that will allow CitySCAPE to create its own brand identity. Communication tools will be applied both for intra and extra-project communications. The specific deliverable will act as a point of reference so as project partners can use the appropriate communication tools, depending on the occasion.

A variety of communication tools have or will be designed, including, but not limited to, templates for project documents and presentations, leaflets and posters, newsletters, videos, press releases, social media campaigns, the project website. All these communication tools will be available either in electronic or (in some cases) printed formats for the partners to use. They will also be used in project events such as plenary meetings and workshops. The CitySCAPE Communication Tools will evolve alongside the project Communication Strategy and Plan as laid down in D9.6.

ANNEX 1: LAYOUT OF THE CITYSCAPE WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

